

Lake Danao Natural Park (LDNP) Fauna Resource Assessment, Ormoc City, Leyte, Philippines

Final Report

Department of Environment
and Natural Resources

Leyte Normal University

Leyte-Samar Sustainable
Development Initiatives

Background

The Protected Area, Wildlife and Coastal Zone Management Service (PAWCZMS) of the Department of Environment and Natural Resources Regional Office No. VIII (DENR RO-8) requested for an inventory of both flora and fauna components of the terrestrial environments at Lake Danao Natural Park, Ormoc City, Leyte in preparation for the formulation of the LDNP Protected Area Management Plan.

Project component setting:

The project component deals with the following:

- *A Wildlife and Terrestrial Vertebrate Baseline Assessment*

The information generated can be used as an input to the formulation of the General Management Plan of Lake Danao Natural Park, Ormoc City, Leyte and used as baseline data for future research undertakings in the area.

Project Team Composition and Contact Details

Facundo Rey M. Ladio – Team Leader
Leyte Normal University, Tacloban City and
email: rey_ladio@hotmail.com

Geraldine O. Macawile – Fauna Component Head
Leyte Samar Sustainable Development Inc.
B-19 L-14 Kassel City Subd., Abucay, Tacloban City
email: macawilegeraldine@yahoo.com

Arnulito C. Viojan – Wildlife (Ornithology) Specialist
DENR RO-8, Sto. Niño Extension, Tacloban City
email: babay57arne@yahoo.com

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the DENR especially the PAWCZMS RO-8 for facilitating the conduct of this project and inviting us to undertake this preliminary LDNP assessment.

Ms. Jobel Gravoso – Protected Area Section Chief, PAWCZMS, DENR-RO-8
CENRO Felino G. Lodevico – LDNP Protected Area Superintendent
Forester Leonardo G. Germano – LDNP Deputy Protected Area Superintendent

We also thank the Leyte Normal University for giving Mr. Ladio the opportunity to work on this project.

Dr Evelyn C. Cruzada – University President
Dr. Conchita P. Avestruz – VP for Administration, Extension and Linkages
Dr. Leonardo G. Oñate – VP for Academic Affairs, Research and Planning
Dr. Marietta B. Manaog – Director for Extension and External Linkages
Prof. Rutchelle B. Enriquez – Director for Research and Planning
Mr. Brendon Joe Vivero – Volunteer Research Aide
Ms. Angeline Meredith Martinez – Volunteer Research Aide
Ms. Marissa Xuxa Macapugas – Volunteer Research Aide

and local guides and cook:

Loloy Narciso
Dondon
Rodito
Marissa Narciso

Photo credits:

Lake Danao (front cover): Rey Ladio
Several photographs: Ronny Boos, Marlito Lamban, Rey Ladio and Arnulito Viojan

Contents

Background	1
Project component setting:	1
Project Team Composition and Contact Details.....	1
Acknowledgements.....	2
Assessment Objectives.....	1
PRELIMINARIES and LIMITATIONS	1
Methodology	2
Fauna Inventory/Survey Methods.....	3
Results and Discussion	6
A. Amphibians and Reptiles	6
B. Birds	10
C. Mammals	15
D. Endemism of Species	18
E. Threatened Species	22
Conclusion.....	34
Conclusion.....	34
Recommendation	35
References:	37

Assessment Objectives

In general, the rapid assessment will determine the flora and fauna resources (terrestrial) of the Lake Danao (Leyte) National Park (LDNP) of Ormoc City, Leyte which is a significant part of the Anonang-Lobi Mountain Range.

Specific objectives of the fauna-component of the study includes the following:

- To inventory and characterize the wildlife assemblage within the Lake Danao National Park. This will focus on the amphibians, birds, reptiles and mammals; and
- To assess and document existing wildlife within the Lake Danao National Park: its status, condition and distribution within the study areas by means of biodiversity indices/parameters, photos, maps and reports.

PRELIMINARIES and LIMITATIONS

Since the project team is given limited time to conduct the assessment, the work to be done will be of a rapid inventory of the existing flora and fauna of Lake Danao National Park; and that a longer term research plan may be developed/submitted and which the DENR and LDNP PAMB would opt to implement.

On July 10 – 15, 2012, the first field work was conducted. The Team worked during days to document birds with nets and point count method, set the nets again at night for the bats and also set the traps for rodents and ground crawling vertebrates to maximize the time the team was on the field. The second field work was from July 27 – 29, 2012 using the same methodology. However the pitfall traps were left open from the first visit until the next.

So with the timing of fieldwork, it is expected that only resident species, especially birds, will be detected since the migration season is several months yet.

The safety of the project team was our major concern, knowing that Sir Leonard Co was murdered several kilometers away only. In our case the team limited sampling sites to areas that we considered safe but representative of the The work of the team may be postponed or cancelled based on the peace and order situation available ecosystems within the LDNP.

Methodology

Lake Danao Natural Park is a protected area under NIPAS. It has several mountain peaks guarding a guitar-shaped natural lake formed by the activity along the Philippine Fault. The Park has an area of about 2,200 ha inclusive of the 170 ha lake at its center. The general elevation of the lake is at 650 m asl, while the mountain peaks surrounding it range from 700 to 1000 m asl.

The dry area of the park is covered by mixed lowland to montane vegetation most of which are second growth. A very small portion is covered with grass, the rest, are mixed agricultural areas planted mostly with abaca, coconut, fruit trees and some vegetables.

Sampling sites were set along Inawasan Creek and at the vicinity of the Camp Site, chosen for their accessibility even during nighttime, and most importantly, due to their strategic locations. However, the Point Count Method (PCM) for birds and opportunistic survey for amphibians and reptiles have covered more areas than the two sampling sites mentioned above.

Fauna Inventory/Survey Methods

1. Point Count Method for Birds

The wildlife inventory was limited to species identification or presence of wildlife species in the survey area. Generally, the survey involved secondary data gathering and actual ground surveys for the avifaunal composition of the Lake Danao Natural Park. The Point Count method was employed in all avifauna data collection. This consists of standing in a specific location and counting number of individual birds (of each species) within a pre-determine area. PCM is used to compare bird differences between sites, monitor changes in bird populations, study seasonal and annual fluctuations in bird populations. The time devoted to point counts must be consistent. Counts should be done within three hours after sunrise. This is when birds are most active. During point counts, record all birds seen and heard within the survey area.

2. Mist Netting for Birds and Volant Mammals (Bats)

Nets that were used are 35-millimeter mono-filament mist nets, 8, 10 or 12 meters in length and two meters in width. Strategic positioning of mist nets was observed at all times to maximize capture rate. Nets were along possible flight paths (i.e., between trees near an opening or possible passageway, on the ground with approximately 30 centimeter clearance for ground dwelling species, etc.). The same mist nets used for birds during the day were utilized to catch bats at night as well.

A maximum of 15 nets per sampling site were set. These nets were operated for a maximum of five consecutive nights/days. Checking during nighttime was performed every two hours interval starting at 1800 h to 2200 h and 0300 h and 0600h. During daytime, checking started at 0600 h to 1800 h with two hours interval also.

3. Trapping of Small Non-Volant Mammals and Herpetofauna

Generally, a maximum of 300 trap nights for a given site is considered as part of a

standardized methodology for the results to be significantly acceptable. However, it should be noted that during the survey proper, it is inevitable that some traps will be misplaced, lost or stolen. Also, trap operation will sometimes be cut short because of unfavorable weather condition or safety concern.

The traps used were a combination of live, snap and pitfall traps. These traps were baited with roasted coconut meat dipped on peanut butter. The traps were placed in areas suspected to be most productive (i.e., along possible runways, near hole or among root tangles and among fallen logs). Checking of traps was performed immediately after dawn (0600 h) while rebaiting was performed late in the afternoon (1600 h). Pitfall traps doubled as traps for crawling vertebrates also.

Captured individuals were processed for their standard biometric measurements which include, tail vent (TV), hind foot (HF), head and body length (HBL), total length (TL) and weight.

4. Opportunistic Capture of Amphibians and Reptiles

Existing trails, rivers and springs and the floating cottages within the park served as survey routes for amphibian and reptile assessment. Whenever amphibians and reptiles were encountered along these routes, they were captured either by hand or other available means. However, sampling was not limited to these areas mentioned above. Sampling was conducted late in the afternoon and in some occasions during the early evening especially when it was raining.

Capture of amphibians and reptiles was primarily through the use of bare hands. For suspected poisonous species, extreme care was followed to avoid any untoward incidents and the use of sticks and other instruments employed to catch snakes. Possible microhabitats were checked (i.e., tree trunk, tree holes, root tangles, water tributaries and small bodies of water) for amphibians and reptiles for opportunities of catching specimens.

5. Interviews (if and when appropriate; optional)

An informal type of meeting were initiated to augment transect, trapping and capture data, which led to a discussion type of information exchange. No questionnaires were given to the respondents but a series of questions were posed to gauge the historical and current distribution of wildlife in the area as well as the local names of wildlife species and other resource use practices by the communities around the park.

Pictures and other visual materials that aid in the identification process were shown to interviewees for positive identification. Whenever doubts were encountered regarding the occurrence of species in the area, they were automatically excluded from the list.

6. Sample Collections, Handling and Recording

Voucher specimens were taken for each species representing both male and female individuals whenever possible and when there is difficulty in determining the species name of captured individuals. The standard biometrics (measurements) was taken first while distinguishing characteristics were noted. The specimens were tagged and given a corresponding catalogue or field number. This tag contained immediate information about the specimen (i.e., catalogue or field number, species, date of collection, sex, collector and place of collection). Catalogue sheets for mammals from the Field Museum of Natural History (FMNH) format were used. This catalogue sheet contains a more comprehensive information regarding the specimen, namely: mode of preparation, approximate age, biometric measurements, collection method; for males- position and size of testes, epididymis and accessory glands; for females- position, number and condition of mammae, vaginal condition, reproductive stage, pubic symphysis, embryos and placental scars; habitat type, and other remarks.

The preservation method followed in this study is a combination of the fluid specimen preparation, study skin and or skeletal specimen.

The appropriate standard biometric measurements were taken for each captured specimen (birds and bats). Specimens collected will be deposited at museums for safekeeping.

Results and Discussion

The species lists provide a window to the vertebrate diversity at Lake Danao Natural Park. This is the product of a rapid resource assessment conducted from 10th -15th and 27th-29th of July 2012. Collectively, 136 species of amphibians, birds, mammals and reptiles were recorded in this assessment.

A. Amphibians and Reptiles

There were 14 species of amphibians from seven families detected at LDNP (Table 1). There are three toad species, *Rhinella marina*, *Megophrys stejnegeri* and *Kaloula conjuncta*, and eleven true frog species. This assemblage contains two introduced species, *Hylarana erythraea* and *Rhinella marina*, two species with widespread distribution, *Occidozyga laevis* and *Rhacophorus pardalis* and ten endemic species (Figure 1).

Table 1. List and distribution range of amphibians at LDNP.

Scientific Name	Common Name	Distribution Range
Family Bufonidae		
<i>Rhinella marina</i> (<i>Bufo marinus</i>)	Marine Toad	Introduced
Family Ceratobatrachidae		
<i>Platymantis corrugatus</i>	Corrugated forest frog	Phil Endemic
<i>P. dorsalis</i>	Common forest ground frog	Phil Endemic
<i>P. rabori</i>	Rabor's Forest Frog	MFR Endemic
Family Dicroglossidae		
<i>Limnonectes leytensis</i>	Philippine Swamp Frog	Phil Endemic
<i>Occidozyga laevis</i>	Puddle Frog	Resident
Family Megophryidae		
<i>Megophrys stejnegeri</i>	Southeast Asian Horned Toad	MFR Endemic
Family Microhylidae		
<i>Kaloula conjuncta</i>	Philippine Narrow-mouthed Toad	MFR Endemic
Family Ranidae		
<i>Hylarana erythraea</i> (<i>Rana erythraea</i>)	Common Green Frog	Introduced

Scientific Name	Common Name	Distribution Range
<i>Hylarana grandocula</i> (<i>Rana grandocula</i>)	Variable back frog	MFR Endemic
Family Rhacophoridae		
<i>Philautus leitensis</i>	Leyte Tree Frog	MFR Endemic
<i>Nyctixalus spinosus</i>	Spiny tree frog	MFR Endemic
<i>Rhacophorus bimaculatus</i>	Asiatic Tree Frog	Phil Endemic
<i>R. pardalis</i>	Gliding Tree Frog	Resident

MFR – Mindanao Faunal Region

However based on the available habitats (like lake, streams, river and higher elevation forest), this list is not complete since there was only a small effort for targeted search on this group. Many species could still be found if there will be more habitats that will be visited and time devoted to amphibian collection.

Figure 1. Number of amphibians at LDNP based on their distribution.

The reptile assemblage at LDNP consists of 17 species from nine families. The species found are composed of one species of freshwater turtle, several lizards - two agamids, three gekkonids, three scincids and one varanid lizard, and snakes ranging from the nonpoisonous constrictor, *Python reticulates*, to the venomous cobras, *Naja samarensis* and *Ophiophagus hannah*.

The *Cuora amboinensis* is the only freshwater turtle present in the area; but is rare since this is usually eaten by local inhabitants. The critically endangered turtle *Siebenrockiella leytensis* (syn. *Heosemys leytensis*), once believed to be found in Leyte, has no records in Leyte nor Samar to date but was rediscovered in Palawan according to Diesmos, *et al.*, (2004).

The *Varanus*, locally known as Halo, have been reassessed and was found that the Bohol, Leyte and Samar *Varanus* is distinct from other *Varanus* from the rest of the country and reclassified from *Varanus salvator* complex to *Varanus cumingi* subspecies *samarensis* (Koch, A., M. Gaulke and W. Böhme. 2010).

There was a snake photographed inside the septic tank/well beside the watch tower site by one of our collaborators (Appendix Figure 1). This snake is designated Snake Sp1 since this could not be identified using the photograph alone without the specimen.

The snakes and lizards listed here is just representative of the specimens and data gathered at LDNP. However, this is not complete since it can be expected that more species will be present given the available habitats at LDNP.

Table 2. List and distribution range of the reptiles at LDNP.

SCIENTIFIC NAME	COMMON/LOCAL NAME	Distribution Range
Family Geoemydidae		
<i>Cuora amboinensis</i>	Southeast Asian Box Turtle/ Bao	Resident
Family Agamidae		
<i>Hydrosaurus pustulatus</i>	Sailfin Lizard/ Ibid	Phil Endemic
<i>Draco mindanensis</i>	Mindanao Flying Lizard	MFR Endemic
Family Gekkonidae		
<i>Gekko gekko</i>	Tokay Gekko / Tuko	Resident
<i>Hemidactylus frenatus</i>	Common House Gecko	Resident
<i>Cosymbotus platyurus</i>	Flat-tailed House Gecko	Resident
Family Scincidae		
<i>Sphenomorphus cumingi</i>	Cuming's Sphenomorphus	Phil Endemic
<i>Sphenomorphus jagori</i>	Jagor's Sphenomorphus	Phil Endemic

<i>Mabuya multifaciata</i>	Common Mabouya/ Tabili	Resident
Family Colubridae		
<i>Bioga angulata</i>	Leyte Cat snake	Phil Endemic
<i>Ahaetulla prasina</i>	Oriental Whip Snake	Resident
<i>Dendrelaphis sp.</i>	Tree Snake	
Family Elapidae		
<i>Naja samarensis</i>	Samar Cobra/ Ibingan	MFR Endemic
<i>Ophiophagus hannah</i>	King Cobra	Resident
Family Boidae		
<i>Python reticulatus</i>	Reticulated Python Sawa	Resident
Family Viperidae		
<i>Trimeresurus flavomaculatus</i>	Pit Viper	Phil Endemic
Snake Sp1		
Family Varanidae		
<i>Varanus cumingi samarensis</i>	Samar Monitor Lizard/ Halo	Subspecies endemic to Leyte, Samar, Bohol

MFR – Mindanao Faunal Region

Distribution Range

Figure 2. Summary of the distribution range of reptiles at LDNP

B. Birds

The A total of 84 birds species belonging to 42 families were recorded at LDNP (Table 3). Dominated mainly by species, usually, observed in forest edges or ecotones. The numbers of individuals per species were highest among Bulbuls, these are omnivore species, despite the fact that they were represented by three (3) species only. The Family Columbidae (doves and pigeons) has the highest species richness among birds; but these groups are highly vulnerable to collection/hunting for food by the locals. The two mentioned bird groups were highly conspicuous; bird calls were usually heard and had high activity throughout the day.

Table 3. List and distribution range of the bird at LDNP.

No.	Scientific Name	Common Name	Distribution Range
	Family Anatidae	Ducks	
1	<i>Anas luzonica</i>	Philippine Mallard	Phil Endemic
	Family Accipitridae	Buzzards, Eagles, Harriers, Hawks, Kites	
2	<i>Haliastur indus</i>	Brahminy Kite	Resident
3	<i>Accipiter trivirgatus</i>	Crested Goshawk	Resident
4	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>	Crested Serpent Eagle	Resident
5	<i>Spizaetus philippensis</i> (<i>Nisaetus philippensis</i>)	Philippine Hawk Eagle	Phil. Endemic
	Family Phasianidae	Pheasants, Quails	
6	<i>Gallus gallus</i>	Jungle Fowl	Resident
	Family Rallidae	Rails, Crakes, Waterhens	
7	<i>Gallirallus torquatus</i>	Barred Rail	Resident
8	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	Common Moorhen	Resident
	Family Columbidae	Doves and Pigeons	
9	<i>Phapitreron leucotis</i>	White-eared Brown Fruit Dove	Phil. Endemic
10	<i>Ptilinopus occipitalis</i>	Yellow-breasted Fruit Dove	Phil. Endemic
11	<i>Ptilinopus leclancheri</i>	Black-chinned Fruit Dove	Phil. Endemic
12	<i>Ducula poliocephala</i>	Pink-bellied Imperial Pigeon	Phil. Endemic
13	<i>Ducula aenea</i>	Green Imperial Pigeon	Resident

No.	Scientific Name	Common Name	Distribution Range
14	<i>Chalcophaps indica</i>	Common Emerald dove	Resident
15	<i>Macropygia phasianella</i>	Reddish Cuckoo Dove	Resident
	Family Psittacidae	Cockatoo and Parrots	
16	<i>Bolbopsittacus lunulatus</i>	Guaiabero	LFR & MFR Endemic
17	<i>Loriculus philippensis</i>	Philippine Hanging Parakeet	Phil.Endemic
18	<i>Prioniturus discurus</i>	Blue-crowned Racquet-Tail	Phil.Endemic
	Family Cuculidae	Cuckoos and Coucals	
19	<i>Cuculus sparverioides</i>	Large Hawk-Cuckoo	Migrant
20	<i>Cacomantis merulinus</i>	Plaintive Cuckoo	Resident
21	<i>Cacomantis variolosus</i>	Brush Cuckoo	Resident
22	<i>Eudynamys scolopacea</i>	Common Koel	Resident
23	<i>Centropus viridis</i>	Philippine Coucal	Phil. Endemic
24	<i>Centropus melanops</i>	Black-faced Coucal	MFR Endemic
	Family Strigidae	Owls	
25	<i>Otus megalotis</i>	Philippine Scops Owl	LFR, MFR & PFR Endemic
26	<i>Bubo philippensis</i>	Philippine Eagle Owl	LFR & MFR Endemic
27	<i>Ninox philippensis</i>	Philippine Hawk-Owl	Phil. Endemic
	Family Podargidae	Frogmouths	
28	<i>Batrachostomus septimus</i>	Philippine Frogmouth	LFR, MFR & PFR Endemic
	Family Caprimulgidae	Nightjars	
29	<i>Caprimulgus manillensis</i>	Philippine Nightjar	Resident
	Family Hemiprocnidae	Treeswifts	
30	<i>Hemiprogne comata</i>	Lesser Treeswift	Resident
	Family Apodidae	Swifts	
31	<i>Collocalia vanikorensis</i>	Island Swiftlet	Resident
32	<i>Collocalia esculenta</i>	Glossy Swiftlet	Resident
33	<i>Collocalia troglodytes</i>	Pygmy Swiftlet	Phil. Endemic
34	<i>Hirundapus celebensis</i>	Purple Needletail	Resident
	Family Trogonidae	Trogons	
35	<i>Herpactes ardens</i>	Philippine Trogon	LFR & MFR Endemic

No.	Scientific Name	Common Name	Distribution Range
	Family Alcedinidae	Kingfishers	
36	<i>Alcedo argentata</i>	Silvery Kingfisher	Migrant
37	<i>Halcyon coromanda</i>	Ruddy Kingfisher	Migrant
38	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	White-throated Kingfisher	Resident
39	<i>Halcyon chloris</i> (<i>Todiramphus chloros</i>)	White-collared Kingfisher	Resident
	Family Meropidae	Bee-eaters	
40	<i>Merops philippinus</i>	Blue-tailed Bee-eater	Resident
	Family Coraciidae	Rollers	
41	<i>Eurystomus orientalis</i>	Dollarbird	Resident
	Family Bucerotidae	Hornbills	
42	<i>Penelopides panini</i> <i>samarensis</i>	Samar Tarictic Hornbill	*Endemic
43	<i>Buceros hydrocorax</i>	Rufous Hornbill	LFR & MFR Endemic
	Family Capitonidae	Barbets	
44	<i>Megalaima haemacephala</i>	Coppersmith Barbet	Resident
	Family Picidae	Woodpeckers	
45	<i>Mulleripicus funebris</i>	Sooty Woodpecker	LFR & MFR Endemic
46	<i>Dendrocopos maculatus</i>	Philippine Pygmy Woodpecker	Phil. Endemic
47	<i>Chrysocolaptes lucidus</i>	Greater Flameback	Resident
	Family Pittidae	Pittas	
48	<i>Pitta erythrogaster</i>	Red-breasted Pitta	Resident
49	<i>Pitta sordida</i>	Hooded Pitta	Resident
	Family Hirundinidae	Swallows	
50	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Barn Swallow	Migrant
51	<i>Hirundo tahitica</i>	Pacific Swallow	Resident
	Family Campephagidae	Cuckoo-shrikes, Trillers	
52	<i>Coracina striata</i>	Bar-bellied Cuckoo-shrike	Resident
53	<i>Lalage nigra</i>	Pied Triller	Resident
	Family Pycnonotidae	Bulbuls	
54	<i>Pycnonotus urostictus</i>	Yellow-wattled Bulbul	LFR & MFR Endemic
55	<i>Pycnonotus goiavier</i>	Yellow-vented Bulbul	Resident

No.	Scientific Name	Common Name	Distribution Range
56	<i>Hypsipetes philippinus (Ixos philippinus)</i>	Philippine Bulbul	Phil. Endemic
	Family Dicruridae	Drongos	
57	<i>Dicrurus hottentottus</i>	Spangled Drongo	Resident
	Family Oriolidae	Orioles, Fairy-bluebirds	
58	<i>Oriolus steerii</i>	Philippine Oriole	Phil. Endemic
59	<i>Oriolus chinensis</i>	Black-naped Oriole	Resident
	Family Irenidae		
60	<i>Irena cyanogaster</i>	Philippine Fairy Bluebird	LFR & MFR Endemic
	Family Corvidae	Crows	
61	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	Large-billed Crow	Resident
	Family Paridae	Tits	
62	<i>Parus elegans</i>	Elegant Tit	Phil. Endemic
	Family Sittidae	Nuthatches	
63	<i>Sitta frontalis</i>	Velvet-fronted Nuthatches	Resident
	Family Timaliidae	Babblers	
64	<i>Ptilocichla mindanensis</i>	Streaked Ground Babbler	MFR Endemic
65	<i>Macronous striaticeps</i>	Brown-tit Babbler	MFR Endemic
	Family Sylviidae	Warblers	
66	<i>Megalurus timoriensis</i>	Tawny Grassbird	Resident
67	<i>Orthotomus castaneiceps</i>	Philippine Tailorbird	Phil. Endemic
	Family Acanthizidae		Endemic
68	<i>Gerygone sulphurea</i>	Yellow-bellied Flyeater	Resident
	Family Rhipiduridae		
69	<i>Rhipidura javanica</i>	Pied Fantail	Resident
70	<i>Rhipidura superciliaris</i>	Blue Fantail	MFR Endemic
	Family Pachycephalidae		
71	<i>Pachycephala philipinensis</i>	Yellow-bellied Whistler	LFR & MFR Endemic
	Family Artamidae		
72	<i>Artamus leucorhynchus</i>	White-breasted Wood-swallow	Resident
	Family Laniidae		
73	<i>Lanius cristatus</i>	Brown Shrike	Migrant

No.	Scientific Name	Common Name	Distribution Range
	Family Sturnidae		
74	<i>Aplonis panayensis</i>	Asian Glossy Starling	Resident
75	<i>Sarcops calvus</i>	Coletto	Phil. Endemic
	Family Nectariniidae		
76	<i>Anthreptes malacensis</i>	Plain-throated Sunbird	Resident
77	<i>Nectarinia jugularis</i>	Olive-backed Sunbird	Resident
78	<i>Aethopyga shelleyi</i>	Lovely Sunbird	Phil. Endemic
	Family Dicaeidae		
79	<i>Dicaeum bicolor</i>	Bicolored Flowerpecker	LFR, MFR & PFR Endemic
80	<i>Dicaeum hypoleucum</i>	Buzzing Flowerpecker	LFR & MFR Endemic
	Family Zoosteropidae		
81	<i>Zosterops everetti</i>	Everett's White-eye	Resident
	Family Passeridae		
82	<i>Passer montanus</i>	Eurasian Tree Sparrow	Resident
	Family Estrildidae		
83	<i>Lonchura malacca</i>	Chestnut Munia	Resident
84	<i>Lonchura leucogastra</i>	White-bellied Munia	Resident

LFR – Luzon Faunal Region; MFR – Mindanao Faunal Region; PFR – Panay Faunal Region

The resident species were the most common among species which accounted to forty four (44) species while thirty-five (35) species were noted to be endemic to the country or to Greater Mindanao Faunal Region (Figure 3). Migratory species are also represented by five (5) species from the terrestrial species that are usually observed in open areas despite the fact that it is several months away to the migration season yet. Nocturnal species were not noticed during the survey except for the Philippine Hawk-owl (*Ninox philippensis*); whose calls during the night were unmistakable. But despite the paucity of observed nocturnal species, ethno-biological surveys suggested and validated their presence in the area. One species of nightjar, possible Philippine Nightjar (*Caprimulgus manillensis*) that usually prefers to fly and prey on insect at dusk near settlements, was heard in one evening also.

Figure 3. Summary of the distribution range of birds species at LDNP

C. Mammals

The result of the survey has confirmed the presence of 22 species of mammals from 11 families and 9 orders within the park (Table 4).

There were eight species of fruit bats of Family Pteropodidae that were either caught on mist nets or observed (Table 2). The most common bat was *Cynopterus brachyotis* with 54 captured individuals. *Ptenochirus minor* comes second with 24 individuals caught on nets with its congener *P. jagori* coming is fourth with only five individuals caught. The fourth was *Haplonycteris fischeri* with 13 individuals netted. Two immature *Rousettus amplexicaudatus* were caught. The presence of young *R. amplexicaudatus* means there is a population of this species at LDNP.

A single individual of the insectivorous vespertilionid Javan Pipistrelle, *Pipistrellus javanicus*, was caught in the net. There were other insectivorous bats observed at dusk and night during the survey but were not caught since mistnets are not very effective in catching them because they can sense the presence of the nets. Other methods such as harp or tunnel trapping are better. During the survey, several improvised harp traps did not catch a bat probably since it was raining the whole night when these traps were opened.

Table 4. List and distribution range of the mammals at LDNP.

Order	Species	Common / Local Name	Distribution Range
Order Insectivora	Family Soricidae		
	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	House Shrew	Resident
Order Dermoptera	Family Cynocephalidae		
	<i>Cyanocephalus volans</i>	Philippine Flying Lemur/ Kagwang	MFR Endemic
Order Chiroptera	Family Pteropodidae		
	<i>Acerodon jubatus</i>	Golden-crowned Flying Fox	Phil Endemic
	<i>Cynopterus brachyotis</i>	Lesser Short-nosed Fruit Bat	Resident
	<i>Haplonycteris fischeri</i>	Philippine Pygmy Fruit Bat	Phil Endemic
	<i>Ptenochirus jagori</i>	Greater Musky Fruit Bat	Phil Endemic
	<i>Ptenochirus minor</i>	Lesser Musky Fruit Bat	MFR Endemic
	<i>Pteropus hypomelanus</i>	Island Flying Fox	Resident
	<i>Pteropus vampyrus</i>	Large Flying Fox	Resident
	<i>Rousettus amplexicaudatus</i>	Geoffroy's Rousette	Resident
	Family Vespertilionidae		
	<i>Pipistrellus javanicus</i>	Javan Pipistrelle	Resident
Order Primates	Family Tarsiidae		
	<i>Tarsius syrichta</i>	Philippine Tarsier/ Mago	MFR Endemic
	Family Cercopithecidae		
	<i>Macaca fascicularis</i> ssp. <i>Philippensis</i>	Philippine Long Tailed Macaque/ Ulot	Phil Endemic
Order Rodentia	Family Sciuridae		

Order	Species	Common / Local Name	Distribution Range
	<i>Exilisciurus concinnus</i>	Philippine Pygmy Squirrel	MFR Endemic
	<i>Sundasciurus philippinensis</i>	Philippine Tree Squirrel	MFR Endemic
	<i>Crunomys melanius</i>	Mindanao Shrew Rat	MFR Endemic
	<i>Rattus everetti</i>	Philippine Forest Rat	Phil Endemic
	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	Asian Black Rat	Resident
Order Carnivora	Family Viverridae	Civets	
	<i>Viverra zangalunga</i>	Malay Civet	Resident
	<i>Paradoxurus hermaphroditus</i>	Palm Civet	Resident
Order Artiodactyla	Family Suidae	Pigs	
	<i>Sus philippensis</i>	Philippine Warty Pig	Phil Endemic
	Family Cervidae	Deer	
	<i>Cervus mariannus (Rusa marianna)</i>	Philippine Deer	Phil Endemic

Two *Crunomys melanius* were caught in the forest above the Camp Site. Other murid species were not caught but their presence were determined by the accounts of local persons. The *Suncus murinus* was observed in front of the LADFA building. Either a squirrel or a murid rodent was observed climbing the tree at the back of the LADFA building also.

The *Paradoxurus hermaphroditus* (Palm Civet Cat/Miro) is seen occasionally by local inhabitants. There were scats observed on trails during the sampling period. Occasionally, *Viverra zangalunga* (Oriental Civet/Garong) is also reportedly observed within the area according to the inhabitants.

The *Tarsius syrichta* and *Cynocephalus volans* were occasionally observed or caught by local inhabitants. But the *Sus philippensis* and *Cervus mariannus* were not sighted recently. This is evident of the decreasing population of these two artiodactyla species.

Most of the mammals species recorded from LDNP are found only here in the Philippines (Figure 3). But nine of these are widespread in the Southeast Asia. The

Macaca fascicularis has a widespread distribution but the *Macaca fascicularis* ssp. *Philippensis* is endemic to the Philippines.

Figure 4. Number of mammals at LDNP based on their distribution range.

D. Endemism of Species

Ten, out of 14 species of amphibians are endemic to the Philippines or a total of 71.43% endemism rate (Figures 1 and 4, and Table 1). Six of these 10 endemic species are found only in the Mindanao Faunal Region/ while the other four species are widespread endemic, *e.i.*, can be found in other major islands of the Philippines also. Two species are widespread within the Sunda area.

There are two introduced amphibians species present at LDNP. These are *Hylarana erythraea* from peninsular Southeast Asia and *Rhinella marina* (syn. *Bufo marinus*) from South America.

Figure 5. Specific endemism rate of amphibians at LDNP.

The reptile assemblage at LDNP consist of eight endemic species, eight non-endemic resident species and two species whose distribution cannot be determined now. Figure 6, below, shows the reptile species endemic to the specific faunal regions within the Philippines.

Figure 6. Specific endemism rate of reptiles at LDNP

Birds, despite their ability of flight show high endemism here in the Philippines. At LDNP, 42% of the bird species are endemic to the Philippines while 52% have widespread distribution while the remaining 6% are migratory birds (Figure 7 and 8).

Figure 7. Specific endemism rate of birds at LDNP

Figure 8. General endemism rate of birds at LDNP

Fifty nine percent of mammals species detected at LDNP are endemic to the country (Figure 9). Only 41% of the mammal species are shared with other Asian nations. Based on the endemism by faunal region Figure 10 shows the data.

Figure 9. General endemism rate of mammal species from LDNP.

Figure 10. Specific endemism rate of mammals at LDNP.

E. Threatened Species

The high endemism among our wildlife species is coupled by the high vulnerability to habitat degradation especially in island nations like the Philippines. This is how the country became one of the biodiversity hotspots in the world (Mittermeier, R., N. Myers and C. Mittermeier, 2000).

Several species found at LDNP are threatened to become extinct in the near future if conditions goes on or worsen. These criteria for listing the conservation status of species are based on the 'Red List' of the Birdlife International (2012), CITES listing of the UNEP-WCMC (2012) and DAO-2004-15 of the DENR.

Among the amphibians, five species, out of 14, are vulnerable to extinction while the rest have stable populations. On the other note, trading is restricted (CITES II) of *Platymantis rabori* (Figure 11 and Table 6).

Table 5. Conservation status of amphibians at LDNP. (C-En – critically En –endangered, NT – near threatened, LC – least concern).

Scientific Name	Common Name	Conservation Status	
		IUCN*	CITES**
Family Bufonidae			
<i>Rhinella marina (Bufo marinus)</i>	Marine Toad	LC	
Family Certobatrachidae			
<i>Platymantis corrugatus</i>	Corrugated forest frog	LC	
<i>P. dorsalis</i>	Common forest ground frog	LC	
<i>P. rabori</i>	Rabor's Forest Frog	Vu	CITES II
Family Dicroglossidae			
<i>Limnonectes leytensis</i>	Philippine Swamp Frog	LC	
<i>Occidozyga laevis</i>	Puddle Frog	LC	
Family Megophryidae			
<i>Megophrys stejnegeri</i>	Southeast Asian Horned Toad	Vu	
Family Microhylidae			
<i>Kaloula conjuncta</i>	Philippine Narrow-mouthed Toad	LC	
Family Ranidae			
<i>Hylarana erythraea (Rana erythraea)</i>	Common Green Frog	LC	
<i>Hylarana grandocula (Rana grandocula)</i>	Variable back frog	LC	
Family Rhacophoridae			
<i>Philautus leitensis</i>	Leyte Tree Frog	Vu	
<i>Nyctixalus spinosus</i>	Spiny tree frog	Vu	
<i>Rhacophorus bimaculatus</i>	Asiatic Tree Frog	Vu	
<i>R. pardalis</i>	Gliding Tree Frog	LC	

*BirdLife International, 2012

**UNEP-WCMC, 2012

Figure 11. Summary of amphibians of LDNP that are on the threatened list

The reptiles of LDNP have four vulnerable species, 11 least concern species and two species that cannot be determined (Figure 12 and Table 6).

Table 6. Conservation status of reptiles at LDNP. (C-En – critically endangered, En – endangered, NT – near threatened, LC – least concern).

SCIENTIFIC NAME	COMMON NAME	CONSERVATION STATUS	
		IUCN*	CITES**
Family Geoemydidae			
<i>Cuora amboinensis</i>	Southeast Asian Box Turtle/ Bao	Vu	CITES II
Family Agamidae			
<i>Hydrosaurus pustulatus</i>	Sailfin Lizard/ Ibid	Vu	CITES II
<i>Draco mindanensis</i>	Mindanao Flying Lizard	Vu	
Family Gekkonidae			
<i>Gekko gekko</i>	Tokay Gekko / Tiki		
<i>Hemidactylus frenatus</i>	Common House Gecko	LC	
<i>Cosymbotus platyurus</i>	Flat-tailed House Gecko		
Family Scincidae			

<i>Sphenomorphus cumingi</i>	Cuming's Sphenomorphus	LC	
<i>Sphenomorphus jagori</i>	Jagor's Sphenomorphus	LC	
<i>Mabuya multifaciata</i>	Common Mabouya/ Tabili		
Family Colubridae			
<i>Bioga angulata</i>	Leyte Cat snake	LC	
<i>Ahaetulla prasina</i>	Elongated-headed tree snake	LC	
<i>Dendrelaphis</i> sp.	Tree Snake		
Family Elapidae			
<i>Naja samarensis</i>	Samar Cobra/ Ibingan	LC	CITES II
<i>Ophiophagus hannah</i>	King Cobra	Vu	CITES II
Family Boidae			
<i>Python reticulatus</i>	Reticulated Python Sawa		CITES II
Family Viperidae			
<i>Trimeresurus flavomaculatus</i>	Pit Viper	LC	CITES II
Family Varanidae			
<i>Varanus cumingi samarensis</i>	Samar Monitor Lizard/ Halo	LC	CITES II

*BirdLife International, 2012

**UNEP-WCMC, 2012

Figure 12. Summary of reptiles of LDNP that are on the threatened list

There were threatened bird species that were observed during the survey. The Guiabero

(*Bolbopsittacus lunulatus*) and Philippine Hanging Parakeet (*Loriculus philippensis*) both are CITES II listed endemic species was among the highly conspicuous bird in the area. Seventeen (17) species are listed either as CITES II, NT- Near threatened, VU- Vulnerable, or included in DAO 2004-15.

Table 7. Conservation status of birds at LDNP. (C-En – critically endangered, En – endangered, NT – near threatened, LC – least concern).

No	Scientific Name	Common Name	Conservation Status	
			IUCN*	CITES**
	Family Anatidae	Ducks		
1	<i>Anas luzonica</i>	Philippine Mallard	Vulnerable	
	Family Accipitridae	Buzzards, Eagles, Harriers, Hawks, Kites		
2	<i>Haliastur indus</i>	Brahminy Kite	LC	CITES II
3	<i>Accipiter trivirgatus</i>	Crested Goshawk	LC	CITES II
4	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>	Crested Serpent Eagle	LC	CITES II
5	<i>Spizaetus philippensis</i> (<i>Nisaetus philippensis</i>)	Philippine Hawk Eagle	Vulnerable	CITES II
	Family Phasianidae	Pheasants, Quails		
6	<i>Gallus gallus</i>	Jungle Fowl	LC	
	Family Rallidae	Rails, Crakes, Waterhens		
7	<i>Gallirallus torquatus</i>	Barred Rail	LC	
8	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	Common Moorhen	LC	
	Family Columbidae	Doves and Pigeons		
9	<i>Phapitreron leucotis</i>	White-eared Brown Fruit Dove	LC	
10	<i>Ptilinopus occipitalis</i>	Yellow-breasted Fruit Dove	LC	
11	<i>Ptilinopus leclancheri</i>	Black-chinned Fruit Dove	LC	
12	<i>Ducula poliocephala</i>	Pink-bellied Imperial Pigeon	LC	
13	<i>Ducula aenea</i>	Green Imperial Pigeon	LC	
14	<i>Chalcophaps indica</i>	Common Emerald dove	LC	
15	<i>Macropygia phasianella</i>	Reddish Cuckoo Dove	LC	
	Family Psittacidae	Cockatoo and Parrots		
16	<i>Bolbopsittacus</i>	Guaiabero	LC	CITES II

No	Scientific Name	Common Name	Conservation Status	
	<i>lunulatus</i>			
17	<i>Loriculus philippensis</i>	Philippine Hanging Parakeet	LC	CITES II
18	<i>Prioniturus discurus</i>	Blue-crowned Racquet-Tail	LC	CITES II
	Family Cuculidae	Cuckoos and Coucals		
19	<i>Cuculus sparverioides</i>	Large Hawk-Cuckoo	LC	
20	<i>Cacomantis merulinus</i>	Plaintive Cuckoo	LC	
21	<i>Cacomantis variolosus</i>	Brush Cuckoo	LC	
22	<i>Eudynamys scolopacea</i>	Common Koel	LC	
23	<i>Centropus viridis</i>	Philippine Coucal	LC	
24	<i>Centropus melanops</i>	Black-faced Coucal	LC	
	Family Strigidae	Owls		
25	<i>Otus megalotis</i>	Philippine Scops Owl	LC	CITES II
26	<i>Bubo philippensis</i>	Philippine Eagle Owl	Vulnerable	CITES II
27	<i>Ninox philippensis</i>	Philippine Hawk-Owl	LC	CITES II
	Family Podargidae	Frogmouths		
28	<i>Batrachostomus septimus</i>	Philippine Frogmouth	LC	
	Family Caprimulgidae	Nightjars		
29	<i>Caprimulgus manillensis</i>	Philippine Nightjar	LC	
	Family Hemiprocnidae	Treeswifts		
30	<i>Hemiprogne comata</i>	Lesser Treeswift	LC	
	Family Apodidae	Swifts		
31	<i>Collocalia vanikorensis</i>	Island Swiftlet	LC	
32	<i>Collocalia esculenta</i>	Glossy Swiftlet	LC	
33	<i>Collocalia troglodytes</i>	Pygmy Swiftlet	LC	
34	<i>Hirundapus celebensis</i>	Purple Needletail	LC	
	Family Trogonidae	Trogons		
35	<i>Herpactes ardens</i>	Philippine Trogon	LC	
	Family Alcedinidae	Kingfishers		
36	<i>Alcedo argentata</i>	Silvery Kingfisher	Vulnerable	

No	Scientific Name	Common Name	Conservation Status	
37	<i>Halcyon coromanda</i>	Ruddy Kingfisher	LC	
38	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	White-throated Kingfisher	LC	
39	<i>Halcyon chloris</i> (<i>Todiramphus chloros</i>)	White-collared Kingfisher	LC	
	Family Meropidae	Bee-eaters		
40	<i>Merops philippinus</i>	Blue-tailed Bee-eater	LC	
	Family Coraciidae	Rollers		
41	<i>Eurystomus orientalis</i>	Dollarbird	LC	
	Family Bucerotidae	Hornbills		
42	<i>Penelopides panini</i> <i>samarensis</i>	Samar Tarictic Hornbill		CITES II
43	<i>Buceros hydrocorax</i>	Rufous Hornbill	NT	CITES II
	Family Capitonidae	Barbets		
44	<i>Megalaima</i> <i>haemacephala</i>	Coppersmith Barbet	LC	
	Family Picidae	Woodpeckers		
45	<i>Mulleripicus funebris</i>	Sooty Woodpecker	LC	
46	<i>Dendrocopos</i> <i>maculatus</i>	Philippine Pygmy Woodpecker	LC	
47	<i>Chrysocolaptes</i> <i>lucidus</i>	Greater Flameback	LC	
	Family Pittidae	Pittas		
48	<i>Pitta erythrogaster</i>	Red-breasted Pitta	LC	
49	<i>Pitta sordida</i>	Hooded Pitta	LC	
	Family Hirundinidae	Swallows		
50	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Barn Swallow	LC	
51	<i>Hirundo tahitica</i>	Pacific Swallow	LC	
	Family Campephagidae	Cuckoo-shrikes, Trillers		
52	<i>Coracina striata</i>	Bar-bellied Cuckoo-shrike	LC	
53	<i>Lalage nigra</i>	Pied Triller	LC	
	Family Pycnonotidae	Bulbuls		
54	<i>Pycnonotus urostictus</i>	Yellow-wattled Bulbul	LC	
55	<i>Pycnonotus goiavier</i>	Yellow-vented Bulbul	LC	
56	<i>Hypsipetes philippinus</i> (<i>Ixos philippinus</i>)	Philippine Bulbul	LC	

No	Scientific Name	Common Name	Conservation Status	
	Family Dicruridae	Drongos		
57	<i>Dicrurus hottentottus</i>	Spangled Drongo	LC	
	Family Oriolidae	Orioles, Fairy-bluebirds		
58	<i>Oriolus steerii</i>	Philippine Oriole	LC	
59	<i>Oriolus chinensis</i>	Black-naped Oriole	LC	
	Family Irenidae			
60	<i>Irena cyanogaster</i>	Philippine Fairy Bluebird	NT	
	Family Corvidae	Crows		
61	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	Large-billed Crow	LC	
	Family Paridae	Tits		
62	<i>Parus elegans</i>	Elegant Tit	LC	
	Family Sittidae	Nuthatches		
63	<i>Sitta frontalis</i>	Velvet-fronted Nuthatches	LC	
	Family Timaliidae	Babblers		
64	<i>Ptilocichla mindanensis</i>	Streaked Ground Babbler	LC	
65	<i>Macronous striaticeps</i>	Brown-tit Babbler	LC	
	Family Sylviidae	Warblers		
66	<i>Megalurus timoriensis</i>	Tawny Grassbird	LC	
67	<i>Orthotomus castaneiceps</i>	Philippine Tailorbird	LC	
	Family Acanthizidae			
68	<i>Gerygone sulphurea</i>	Yellow-bellied Flyeater	LC	
	Family Rhipiduridae			
69	<i>Rhipidura javanica</i>	Pied Fantail	LC	
70	<i>Rhipidura superciliaris</i>	Blue Fantail	LC	
	Family Pachycephalidae			
71	<i>Pachycephala philipinensis</i>	Yellow-bellied Whistler	LC	
	Family Artamidae			
72	<i>Artamus leucorhynchus</i>	White-breasted Wood-swallow	LC	
	Family Laniidae			
73	<i>Lanius cristatus</i>	Brown Shrike	LC	

No	Scientific Name	Common Name	Conservation Status	
	Family Sturnidae			
74	<i>Aplonis panayensis</i>	Asian Glossy Starling	LC	
75	<i>Sarcops calvus</i>	Coletto	LC	
	Family Nectariniidae		LC	
76	<i>Anthreptes malacensis</i>	Plain-throated Sunbird	LC	
77	<i>Nectarinia jugularis</i>	Olive-backed Sunbird	LC	
78	<i>Aethopyga shelleyi</i>	Lovely Sunbird	LC	
	Family Dicaeidae			
79	<i>Dicaeum bicolor</i>	Bicolored Flowerpecker	LC	
80	<i>Dicaeum hypoleucum</i>	Buzzing Flowerpecker	LC	
	Family Zoosteropidae			
81	<i>Zosterops everetti</i>	Everett's White-eye	LC	
	Family Passeridae			
82	<i>Passer montanus</i>	Eurasian Tree Sparrow	LC	
	Family Estrildidae			
83	<i>Lonchura malacca</i>	Chestnut Munia	LC	
84	<i>Lonchura leucogastra</i>	White-bellied Munia	LC	

Figure 13. Summary of birds present at LDNP that are on the threatened list

Among the mammals, the *Acerodon jubatus* is endangered with most of its habitat threatened also. There are three species listed in the vulnerable category and two in the near threatened category (Figure 14 and Table 8).

The *Acerodon jubatus* is also listed in the Appendix I of CITES (Figure 15 and Table 8). Five of the other mammal species are in the CITES II. The *Paradoxurus hermaphrodites* is listed in Appendix III also.

Table 8. Conservation status of mammals at LDNP. (C-En – critically endangered, En – endangered, NT – near threatened, LC – least concern).

Order	Species	Common / Local Name	Conservation Status	
			IUCN	CITES
Order Insectivora	Family Soricidae			
	<i>Suncus murinus</i>	House Shrew	LC	
Order Dermoptera	Family Cynocephalidae			
	<i>Cynocephalus volans</i>	Philippine Flying Lemur/ Kagwang	LC	CITES II
Order Chiroptera	Family Pteropodidae			

Order	Species	Common / Local Name	Conservation Status	
	<i>Acerodon jubatus</i>	Golden-crowned Flying Fox	En	CITES I
	<i>Cynopterus brachyotis</i>	Lesser Short-nosed Fruit Bat/ Kwapnit	LC	
	<i>Haplonycteris fischeri</i>	Philippine Pygmy Fruit Bat	LC	
	<i>Ptenochirus jagori</i>	Greater Musky Fruit Bat	LC	
	<i>Ptenochirus minor</i>	Lesser Musky Fruit Bat	LC	
	<i>Pteropus hypomelanus</i>	Island Flying Fox	LC	CITES II
	<i>Pteropus vampyrus</i>	Large Flying Fox	NT	CITES II
	<i>Rousettus amplexicaudatus</i>	Geoffroy's Rousette	LC	
	Family Vespertilionidae			
	<i>Pipistrellus javanicus</i>	Javan Pipistrelle	LC	
Order Primates	Family Tarsiidae			
	<i>Tarsius syrichta</i>	Philippine Tarsier/ Mago	NT	CITES II
	Family Cercopithecidae			
	<i>Macaca fascicularis</i>	Long Tailed Macaque/ Ulot	LC	CITES II
Order Rodentia	Family Sciuridae			
	<i>Exilisciurus concinnus</i>	Philippine Pygmy Squirrel	LC	
	<i>Sundasciurus philippinensis</i>	Philippine Tree Squirrel	LC	
	Family Muridae			
	<i>Crunomys melanius</i>	Mindanao Shrew Rat	Vulnerable	
	<i>Rattus everetti</i>	Philippine Forest Rat	LC	
	<i>Rattus tanezumi</i>	Asian Black Rat	LC	
Order Carnivora	Family Viverridae	Civets		
	<i>Viverra zibetha</i>	Malay Civet	LC	
	<i>Paradoxurus hermaphroditus</i>	Palm Civet	LC	CITES III
Order Artiodactyla	Family Suidae	Pigs		
	<i>Sus philippensis</i>	Philippine Warty Pig	Vulnerable	
	Family Cervidae	Deer		
	<i>Cervus mariannus (Rusa marianna)</i>	Philippine Deer	Vulnerable	

Figure 14. Summary of LDNP mammals that are on the Red List of threatened species

Figure 15. CITES listed mammal species present at LDNP

Conclusion

Mammals and reptiles abound in the area based on our ethno-biological survey. Wild pig's tracks were noted in some areas between some survey areas. Monitor Lizard (*Varanus salvator*) and Philippine Sailfin Lizard (*Hydrosaurus pustulatus*) are believed to be in existence in the area. The mammalian and reptilians species (refer to Fig. 2) included in this are mostly from the ethno-biological survey and by tracks and droppings noticed along the transect routes. The use of live traps and mist nets could have augmented the number of volant species encountered in the area, however this can be attributed to the unavailability of trapping equipments, in terms of number of species. A total of 12 mammalian species of which seven (7) are endemic or 58% with the five (5) remaining species or 42% are resident species. However, nine (9) or 75% are listed as threatened species in general consideration.

Conclusion

The survey results show that the study area has a high diversity of vertebrate fauna with correspondingly high numbers of birds and mammals, although reptiles and amphibians are poorly represented in the survey. The Point Count Method, mist-netting, trapping and ethnobiological survey revealed 84 species of birds, 22 mammalian species, and 14 amphibians and at 18 reptile species.

This survey has captured *Pipistrellus javanicus* for the first time in Leyte. Although this insectivore bat is widespread in distribution, this is a new record at Leyte.

The amphibians have the highest endemism at 71%, followed mammals with 60%. Among reptiles 44.44% are endemic. The birds are the last among the four groups in terms of endemism with 42%.

Unfortunately many vertebrate species found at LDNP are threatened. Hence, the protection of this park and other areas will be of great help in the conservation effort of these threatened species.

Recommendation

- Generally, the results of a one shot survey coupled with limited time do not show yet the real species composition and population of the area due to the limited data collection. A deeper population study, if conducted in the future, will reveal the population trend of species in the park. Thus, there should be a follow-up detailed resource assessment that must be conducted, especially on different seasons, to have in-depth knowledge of the real fauna composition at LDNP.
- Mapping of wildlife habitat especially of threatened species; and determining their life history is the way towards biodiversity conservation/protection.
- As such, it is necessary to have an environmental conservation action plan created in consultation with all stakeholders. This conservation plan should be an integral part of the development and land use plans for the LDNP. The resulting conservation action plan will be more effective in addressing the conservation need in the park when local stakeholders are empowered and feels a sense of ownership and responsibility.
- Ecotourism, while it can bring positive impact to the wellbeing of the park and its inhabitants, can have negative impact, too; especially if this is not conducted properly. Hence, it will be best if the carrying capacity of the park can be assessed first before ecotourism can be permitted and the tour guides must have proper training to be wardens for the environment.
- In recognition that any development, even ecotourism will impact the environment, there should be a continual an environmental monitoring program. In this way, indices of abundance and distribution of plants and animals will be regularly

monitored and this will enable environmental workers to respond to drastic decline in these populations.

- The management of the LDNP especially the local tour operators and guides must be informed about the occurrence and location of threatened species in the park to avoid unnecessarily disturbance of the biota. Birdwatching/nature trails and viewing decks can be established at strategic locations to minimized tourist impact on the fragile ecosystem.
- Educational activities on the environment are necessary to increase the local people's cooperation in conservation efforts. Video footages and other audio-visual materials can be used to produce print and broadcast information and educational materials that highlight the diversity of wildlife and the conservation importance of the park.
- To encourage the proper attitude and behavior towards the environment of tourists and visitors to the LDNP, the visitor center can be strengthened and must conduct lectures about the rich biodiversity of the park and teach tourist how to behave while in the park to minimize disturbance of wildlife species. This, together with a knowledgeable tour guide will help preserve the balance in the park.

References:

- Beukema, Wouter. 2011. Herpetofauna of disturbed forest fragments on the lower Mt. Kitanglad Range, Mindanao Island, Philippines. *Salamandra* 47(2) 90–98
- BirdLife International 2012. *Red List*. In: IUCN 2012. IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2012.2. <www.iucnredlist.org>. Downloaded on 2 November 2012.
- Brown, R. and S. Guttman. 2002. Phylogenetic systematics of the *Rana signata* complex of Philippine and Bornean stream frogs: reconsideration of Huxley's modification of Wallace's Line at the Oriental–Australian faunal zone interface. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 2002, 76, 393–461.
- Denzer, W., K. Henle, M. Gaulke, J. Margraf, P. P. Milan. 1994. Annotated checklist of the reptiles and amphibians of Leyte, Philippines with notes on their ecology and conservation (Abstract). In AGRIS-FAO. 2012. AGRIS Database. <http://agris.fao.org/agris-search/search/display.do?f=2000%2FPH%2FPH00003.xml%3BPH2000100451>. Downloaded on 12 November 2012
- Diesmos, A., G. Gee, M. Diesmos, R. Brown, P. Widmann, and J. Dimalibot. 2004. Rediscovery of the Philippine Forest Turtle, *Heosemys leytensis* (Chelonia; Bataguridae), from Palawan Island, Philippines. *Asiatic Herpetological Research* Vol. 10, pp. 22-27
- Haring, E., K. Kvaløy, J.-O. Gjershaug, N. Røv, and A. Gamau. 2007. Convergent evolution and paraphyly of the hawk-eagles of the genus *Spizaetus* (Aves, Accipitridae) – phylogenetic analyses based on mitochondrial markers. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research* 45(4), 353–365
- Heaney, L. R. and E. A. Rickart. 1990. Correlations of clades and clines: geographic, altitudinal, and phylogenetic distribution patterns among the Philippine mammals. In Peters, G. and R. Hutterer. eds. Symposium on vertebrate biogeography and speciation in the tropics, Bonn Mus. Alexanderkoenig, pp 321-332
- Heaney, L. R., D. S. Balete, M. L. Dolar, A. C. Alcala, A. T. L. Dans, P. C. Gonzales, N. R. Ingle, M. V. Lepiten, W. L. R. Oliver, P. S. Ong, E. A. Rickart, B. R. Tabaranza, Jr., and R. C. B. Uzzurum. 1998. *A synopsis of the mammalian fauna of the Philippine Islands*. Fieldiana Zoology new series, 88:1-61
- Ingle, N. R. and L. R. Heaney. 1992. A key to the bats of the Philippine Islands. Fieldiana Zoology new series No. 69
- IUCN. 2008. *2008 IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*. <www.iucnredlist.org>. Downloaded on 27 October 2008.
- Kennedy, R. S., P. C. Gonzales, E.C. Dickinson, H.C. Miranda and T.H. Fisher. 2000. A

guide to the birds of the Philippines. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Koch, A., M. Gaulke and W. Böhme. 2010. Unraveling the underestimated diversity of Philippine water monitor lizards (Squamata: *Varanus salvator* complex), with the description of two new species and a new subspecies. *Zootaxa* 2446: 1–54

Mittermeier, R., N. Myers and C. Mittermeier. 2000. *Hotspots: Earth's Biologically Richest and Most Endangered Terrestrial Ecoregions*. Conservation International

UNEP-WCMC. 2012. UNEP-WCMC Species Database: CITES-Listed Species.
<http://www.unep-wcmc-apps.org/isdb/CITES> . Downloaded 3 November 2012.